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LEADERSHIP IN PEOPLE MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Leadership in people management is permeated with strategic nuances that are fatal at the beginning of this 21st century and it is important to study theories as a way of improving for the challenges that arise in the future. Innovation and performance are the keywords of these new times and to understand them better, a critical revisit to the fathers of modern administration is necessary. In short, everyone contributed to administration science by developing various methods and theories that aimed to increase efficiency and effectiveness in organizations, through the application of scientific, managerial and organizational principles.

Keywords: Organization, People Management, Leadership

INTRODUCTION

Based on the theoretical and empirical field of research, the phenomenon of leadership has developed in a variety of ways, depending on the conceptions and methodological preferences adopted by researchers. Currently, approaches to the topic emphasize that it is necessary to deepen the knowledge of this issue, evaluating it as a relationship, a reciprocity between leader and followers on social, symbolic and cultural levels.

In any case, the topic has been addressed since the emergence of leaders, and this dates back to the time when human beings, in search of security, exchanged their freedom to live alone for living in a group, forming what we know today as society.

Scholtes (1999) argues that leadership includes not only the presence and spirit of the individual who commands, but also the relationship he forms with the people he leads. The author also claims that the leader of the current millennium must understand systems if he intends to adequately manage his decision-making.

Appreciating this approach, it is clear that business leadership is different from the position, being both the accumulation of personal 'attributes' (firmness, charisma, perseverance, vision, etc.) and an 'art', that is, a personal ability to convince that something can be aimed for and undertaken.

Therefore, leadership should not be confused with direction or management, which must be led by a good leader who does not always occupy the role of director or manager within an organization. The leader must be present at all hierarchical levels and in all areas of activity.

DEVELOPMENT

For Chiavenato (2003a, p.123), "leadership is one of the most researched and studied topics in recent decades". Leadership in organizations can be interpreted as a complex social phenomenon, having been frequently and traditionally conceptualized in terms of: personality traits, behavioral styles and contingency factors – contingency or situational theories explore the variables that surround the leadership process, without leave aside the

different types of behavior of leaders (DAVEL and MACHADO, 2001).

Davel and Machado (2001) further clarify that the so-called "trait theory" is one of the pioneering theories in the study of the phenomenon of Leadership, predominating until the 1940s, and mainly emphasized the personal qualities of the leader.

Later, at the beginning of the 1950s, behavioral scientists began to worry about the aspects that characterize the leader's behavioral style, directing their attention to what the leader does, showing interest in the types of behavior he adopted, which would be responsible for increasing his effectiveness when directing his followers.

Between the 1960s and the early 1980s, situational or contingency approaches highlighted the fact that the emergence and maintenance of an effective leader must consider aspects that are part of the environment within which the leader is acting. This contingency theory emphasizes people, tasks, technology, administration and the environment, forming a dependency on each other. It approaches organizations as open systems that balance their internal needs with environmental circumstances.

According to Robbins (2005, p. 309), "[...] the contingency model proposes that the effectiveness of the group's performance depends on the adequacy between the leader's style and how much control the situation provides him".

The combination of these elements should determine the type of technique that should be used by management and, thus, identify the individual's leadership style. It becomes necessary to adapt the person to the situation.

PERSONALITY TRAIT THEORY

Leadership approached according to "personality traits" started from the thought that certain individuals have a special combination of these traits. This could be used to identify potential future leaders.

A leader is someone who presents outstanding personality characteristics through which he or she

can influence the behavior of other people. These theories were influenced by the “great man” theory defended by Carlyle to explain that the world’s progress was the product of personal achievements of some men who dominate the history of humanity (CHIAVENATO, 2003, p.123).

Exceptionally, the most striking personality traits were identified as signs of Leadership. In this simplicity of verification, for Chiavenato (2003a), this theory believed in the similarity between:

- Physical traits – Energy, appearance and weight seemed to reflect similarity between people with leadership traits.
- Intellectual traits – The most striking traits are: adaptability, aggressiveness, enthusiasm and self-confidence.
- Social traits – These deal with interpersonal skills, in addition to administrative skills, also highlighting the tendency towards cooperation.
- Traits related to the task – Disposition to work that can be reflected in: drive for achievement, persistence and initiative.

However, it is worth mentioning that Robbins (2005) explains that some notorious leaders, such as Hitler, Napoleon and Lincoln, did not have characteristics that prove this theory. This led to it being criticized, leading researchers to explore other approaches to understanding Leadership.

In this way, the study of Leadership exposed an evolution of concepts whose initial idea – seen only as “personality traits” (Chiavenato, 2003, p.123) – gave way to its discovery as a potential that can be fully developed, fostered and stimulated.

LEADERSHIP STYLES

Employees work towards satisfying their needs, however, not everyone is always able to achieve their goals, resulting in a greater or lesser degree of satisfaction. When it comes to the topic of leadership, this is no different.

Thus, the study of leadership exposes an

evolution of concepts in which the initial idea of leadership, seen as a personality trait, gave way to the discovery of leadership characterized as a potential that can be fully developed, fostered and stimulated. Organizational results are influenced, most of the time, by the leadership styles of today’s professionals.

In fact, the company’s performance and, certainly, its position in the market depend on the leadership style assumed by the business leader. According to Belluzzo (2002 apud PESTANA et al., 2003, p.81), leadership can be divided into autocratic, democratic and liberal, as shown in the Table below:

TABLE – TABLE OF LEADERSHIP

SITUAÇÃO	AUTOCRÁTICA	DEMOCRÁTICA	LIBERAL
Decisões	Decide sozinho	Equipe toma decisões, o líder assiste e participa	Equipes tomam decisões, participação mínima do líder
Programa de trabalho	Determina como deve ser executado	Equipe delinea os procedimentos e o líder apoia	Líder esclarece dúvidas quando necessário
Divisão do trabalho	Determina quem deve executar e o que	Equipe decide sobre a divisão	O líder não participa
Participação do líder	É "pessoal", domina elogios e críticas	É participativo e objetivo, elogios/críticas compartilhados	Participa só quando solicitado

Source: Beluzzo (2002 apud PESTANA et al., 2003, p.81)

Leadership styles may or may not facilitate a team’s performance, regardless of studies concerning the development of leadership skills. However, when considering leadership styles, profiles are initially identified whose behaviors relate to postures described in the three groups above:

- Autocratic: For Stoner and Freeman (1994), the autocratic style is one in which only the leader decides, setting the organization’s guidelines without any participation from the group. The group’s employees are closely supervised to ensure that tasks are carried out satisfactorily. It uses authoritarianism, deciding and just communicating to the group. It is centralizing, possessive and controlling, which exemplifies the famous saying “those who can command, obey those who have sense”.
- Democrat: The democratic style seeks everyone’s participation and encourages those led to carry out tasks. There is an appreciation of interpersonal relationships. Group members are

free to give their opinions and suggestions, allowing greater participation and sharing power.

- Liberal: The so-called Laissez-Faire presents completely liberal characteristics in which the manager allows the group to make all decisions. For Vergara (2005), they are negligent managers who are not responsible for decisions or results. This style does not get involved in the activities of its employees and exerts small influences.

Depending on the leader's behavior, his subordinate will have a greater or lesser degree of power to make decisions. In authoritarian leadership, the leader normally makes decisions and announces them, while in democratic leadership there is greater independence and freedom of action for people, in which they have more responsibilities and more knowledge to face problems.

In short, the leader must seek a balance between leadership styles, in order to achieve the best performance from employees, without frustrating their desires. Your behavior should fluctuate depending on the situation. At times, employees desire and are prepared to take on a greater level of responsibilities, and the leader must give them more freedom in decision-making. At other times, employees are not interested in working, demanding more authoritarian behavior from the leader. The way a leader should act depends on factors such as the maturity of employees, group relationships and the nature of the tasks, among others. (STONER and FREEMAN, 1994).

When characterizing leadership, Rowe (2002), according to the table below, focuses on strategic leaders, distinguishing them from managerial and visionary leaders. According to him, strategic people dream and try to make their dreams come true, being a combination of the managerial leader, who never stops dreaming, and the visionary, who only dreams. This type of leader will possibly create more value than the combination of a visionary and managerial leader.

BOARD – STRATEGIC, VISIONARY AND MANAGEMENT LEADERSHIP

LEADERS STRATEGIC	LEADERS LEADING	VISIONARIES MANAGERS
• They combine, in synergy, managerial	• They are proactive, shape ideas,	• They are conservative, adopting

<p>leadership and visionary leadership.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasize ethical behavior and values-based decisions. • Supervise operational (routine) and strategic (long-term) responsibilities. • Formulate and implement. Strategies for immediate impact and maintaining long-term goals to ensure long-term survival, growth and viability. • They have high and optimistic expectations regarding the performance of their superiors, peers, subordinates and themselves. • They use strategic and financial control, placing emphasis on the <u>strategic</u>. • They use and alternate the use of tacit and explicit knowledge in relation to the individual and the organization. • Use linear and non-linear thinking patterns. • They believe in adopting strategies, that is, their strategic decisions make a difference in their organizations and work environment. 	<p>change what people think is desirable, possible and necessary.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work to improve strategies and new approaches to old problems; occupy high-risk positions. • They care about ideas; They relate to people in an intuitive and understanding way. • They feel alienated from their work environment, they work in organizations, but are not part of them; their perception of themselves is not linked to work. • They influence the attitudes and opinions of people within the organization. • They are concerned with ensuring the future of the organization, mainly through the development and management of people. • They are more linked to complexity, ambiguity and information overload; committed to multifunctional and integrative tasks. • They know less than experts in their functional area. • They are more likely to make decisions based on values. • They are more willing to invest in innovations and human capital and to create and maintain an efficient culture to ensure long-term viability. • Emphasize tacit knowledge and develop strategies as a common form of tacit knowledge that encourages the achievement of a goal. 	<p>passive attitudes towards goals; goals arise from necessity, not from desires and dreams; goals are based on the past.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They consider work to be a facilitating process that involves the integration of ideas and people who interact to define strategies. • They relate to people according to their roles in the decision-making process. • They believe they are conservative and regulators of the status quo; their perception of themselves is linked to the organization. • They influence the actions and decisions of the people with whom they work. • They get involved in situations and contexts characteristic of day-to-day activities. • They care about and feel good about functional areas of responsibility. • They are experts in their functional area. • Are less likely to make decisions based on values • Support and adopt a minimum price stance in the short term in order to increase financial performance. • Focus on managing the exchange and combination of explicit knowledge and ensuring compliance with operating procedures. • They use linear thinking. • They believe in determinism, that is, the choices they make are determined by the external and internal environment.
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Source: Rowe (2002)

Managerial leaders seek the organization's financial stability in the short term. Consequently, they maintain the status quo and do not invest in innovations that can change and increase the organization's resources in the long term. Visionaries, on the other hand, seek the long-term viability of the organization, through change and innovation, in order to create long-term value (ROWE, 2002).

Integrating these two types of leadership can create a team of two or more individuals who can exercise strategic leadership and create value for the organization. However, a single individual who combines, in synergy, the qualities of a visionary and a manager will achieve maximum value creation for his organization.

MANAGEMENT

In the organizational context, caution must be taken when characterizing a leader, as a leader should not be confused with a manager. "The leader is the one who deals with matters that are not tangible at the organizational level, while the manager takes care of concrete points." (ARAÚJO and GARCIA, 2009, p.341).

For the authors, a better understanding of the definitions between leader and manager can be found in the following table.

TABLE – LEADERSHIP

Leader	Manager
Leadership is connecting people in the organization to your business.	Management is putting the organization's people to work in your business.
Leadership is getting and keeping people in the organization acting and working like owners.	Management is about getting and working like people in the organization.
Leadership is the art of making others want to do something that you are convinced should be done.	Management is the art of getting people to do something that you are convinced should be done.
Leadership is the art of mobilizing others to strive for shared aspirations.	Management is the art of mobilizing others to fight.
Leadership is the art of obtaining desired, agreed and expected results through engaged people.	Management is the art of obtaining desired, agreed and expected results through people.

Source: Araújo and Garcia (2009, p.341)

According to Araújo and Garcia (2009), a good leader must transmit confidence to his followers. And among the characteristics that can help you attract such trust are:

- Self-leadership – The leader's trajectory must begin with him leading himself.
- Sharing – This is the key characteristic for understanding the relationship between power and Leadership, since when observed as a leader, you will certainly have a certain type of power. However, for there to be Leadership, it must necessarily be shared.
- Courage – For the leader it is an indispensable attribute, as having courage, in addition to representing a courageous person, makes others believe in your willingness and determination, thus developing a relationship of trust, that is, the basis for the existence of Leadership.
- Focus – The concentration that must be on a leader's final objective. No obstacle, no matter how great, can divert you from your vision.
- Change – Prerequisite for Leadership. "You cannot think about the hypothesis of there being leaders and followers if the objective is to remain at the same level" (ARAÚJO and GARCIA, 2009, p 343).

Consequently, it has become imperative that a leader has, among his basic characteristics, the ability to adapt to adverse situations and, above all, be capable, for the benefit of the team, of acquiring new convictions. The same authors conclude that for changes to be "realized", four basic policies must be followed:

- 1st policy – Abandonment of yesterday: the first and most relevant step for change to happen.
- 2nd policy – Continuous improvement (kaizen): The idea is to believe that performance can always be improved.
- 3rd policy – Exploration of success: As much as it is recommended to solve, whenever possible, the organization's problems, it is suggested that for changes to occur, opportunities must be at the forefront.

- 4th policy – Systematic innovation: The objective is not to reinforce the concept of a leader, always innovative, but to create a spirit of innovation in the organizational sphere.

Such measures, when in total agreement, can differentiate the true profile of a leader. In this line of reasoning, the leader's fundamental focus is on getting people (followers) to believe in a purpose, and especially, evaluating this purpose among their followers, then making choices that most share these goals with them. Therefore, Leadership is a matter of reducing group uncertainty. The behavior through which this reduction is achieved is choice (CHIAVENATO, 2009).

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

An increasingly competitive world is expected. Companies of the future will survive if they have efficiency in their processes, becoming agile, with quick decision-making and becoming less bureaucratic. However, this will only be possible with the achievement of managerial maturity. Excellence in management will continue to be a great solution for sustaining organizations, after all, if nowadays companies are evaluated by the efficiency of their management, in the future no one will invest in a company that does not pay attention to the evolution of the business efficiently and sustainably.

Therefore, the professionalization of organizations is, and will continue to be, the driving force for small, medium and large companies. Therefore, there will be no company that will worry about evaluating constant results in its internal and external processes. Another strong trend will also be the solution for some companies that do not evolve to this new panorama. These are mergers, which seem to be an alternative for growth for large organizations.

You cannot think about achieving success without knowledge of the world in which you are active. Therefore, there is no way for a professional to prosper in any area of activity without investigating what is around them, and, furthermore, one cannot imagine being a results leader who does not have the ability to build winning strategies.

Therefore, the ability to deliver results inevitably depends on Market Intelligence. Results without a strategy can cost more or become perishable. Sustainable results, which guarantee the continuity of the business, are achieved by a well-designed strategy, designed by professionals who live in the market, who have the ability to think globally.

All that is expected in a career is to achieve good results. All the employee wants in his personal life is to achieve good results. The change between these aspects is each person's purpose, however, in the end we live to achieve results in all areas of life. This is precisely why this intelligence was the most mentioned as being a predominant factor for the professional of the future.

New professionals must have the ability to think about results, whether in choosing a profession, leading their team, or in their own business. The corporate world will have space for those professionals who want to achieve and make things happen; and, naturally, it will discard passivity and conformism.

CONCLUSION

What is exposed in this article concerns the way in which leadership should be exercised, observing its modalities and respecting the specificities of each organization. The corporate world is increasingly competitive, which requires better preparation and observance of styles that can help determine how employees will understand how that company is run.

Having met the main objectives and motivation of the article, it is important to verify leadership as an element of communication between articulation that can provide better conditions for the consolidation of the sector and, consequently, results that can consolidate the company, its brand and the products with which it distributes to the various markets whether locally, regionally or globally.

Finally, this change meets the growth in demand from players and countries that place more pressure on leadership that must be exercised in accordance with the expectations of society, employees and the commercial world, as the value of the company

depends on the form of how their leadership is exercised.

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